

Kinetics of Bromide catalysed Oxidation of Dextrose by Cerium(IV) in Aqueous Sulphuric Acid Solution

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Kinetics of bromide catalysed oxidation of dextrose by Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulphuric acid medium show first order dependence each in dextrose and cerium(IV). The reaction rate decreases on increasing the concentration of hydrogen ion. The increase in $[HSO_4^-]$ or $[SO_4^{2-}]$ decreases the rate. The bromide ion shows positive catalytic effect on the reaction rate. The value of activation energy has been calculated and a suitable mechanism confirming to the kinetic data is proposed.

A survey of literature has shown that kinetics of bromide catalysed oxidation of dextrose by Ce^{IV} has not been studied. This paper deals with the kinetic study of bromide catalysed oxidation of dextrose by Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulphuric acid medium.

Results and Discussion

Order of reaction with respect to Ce^{IV} : The reactions were studied at different concentrations of ceric ammonium sulphate by isolation method. When the concentration of dextrose was in excess, the reaction followed a first order rate law. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) are listed in Table 1. The variation of ceric ions concentration had practically no effect on the rate constant, thus the order with respect to Ce^{IV} was unity.

Order of reaction with respect to dextrose : The reactions were studied at different concentrations of dextrose and at fixed concentrations of the other reactants. The values of k_1 were determined at fixed concentration of Ce^{IV} for different concentrations of dextrose. The results (Table 1) show that the velocity constant is directly proportional to the concentration of dextrose. The values of k_2 obtained on dividing k_1 values by concentrations of dextrose, are practically constant

(Table 1), which show first order dependence on dextrose.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON VELOCITY CONSTANT

Temp. = 40°, [KBr] = 5.0×10^{-3} M					
[Ce^{IV}] $\times 10^3$ M	[Dextrose] $\times 10^3$ M	Ionic strength μ	[H_2SO_4] $\times 10$ M	k_1 $\times 10$ min ⁻¹	k_2 mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
1.00	12.50	1.68	5.00	0.23	—
2.00	12.50	1.68	5.00	0.23	—
2.50	2.60	1.55	5.00	0.09	3.46
2.50	6.00	1.55	5.00	0.24	4.00
2.50	10.00	1.55	5.00	0.31	3.10
2.50	12.50	1.55	5.00	0.40	3.20
2.50	21.00	1.55	5.00	0.70	3.33
2.50	25.00	—	6.00	5.19	—
2.50	25.00	—	7.00	4.50	—
2.50	25.00	—	8.00	4.07	—
2.50	25.00	—	9.00	3.72	—
2.50	25.00	—	10.00	3.50	—
4.00	12.50	1.68	5.00	0.26	—
5.00	12.50	1.68	5.00	0.24	—

Effect of ionic strength, hydrogen ions and bromide ions : The results of various experiments at different ionic strengths of the medium indicate

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that the values of k_1 decrease on increasing the ionic strength of the medium at constant $[H^+]$ (Table 2). The values of k_1 also decrease on increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid at varying ionic strength (Table 1). Addition of potassium bromide shows positive catalytic effect of Br^- ion on the reaction rate. The values of k_1 increase on increasing $[Br^-]$ (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF BROMIDE ION CONCENTRATION, IONIC STRENGTH AND TEMPERATURE ON REACTION VELOCITY CONSTANT

$[Dextrose] = 12.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.5 M$

Temp. °C	$[Br^-] \times 10^3 M$	Ionic strength μ	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$
35	5.00	1.55	1.90
40	3.00	1.56	2.41
40	6.00	1.56	2.42
40	12.00	1.56	2.57
40	15.00	1.56	2.70
40	18.00	1.56	2.86
40	5.00	1.55	4.00
40	5.00	1.70	2.96
40	5.00	1.85	2.67
40	5.00	1.93	2.56
40	5.00	1.55	3.64
45	5.00	1.55	5.11
50	5.00	1.55	7.45

Effect of bisulphate and sulphate ions : The state of Ce^{IV} in H_2SO_4 medium is complicated by the fact that sulphate being a better ligand can combine with Ce^{IV} to a varying degree forming various species. Several investigations¹ revealed that in H_2SO_4 medium, ceric sulphate exists mainly as $Ce(SO_4)^{2+}$, $Ce(SO_4)_2$, $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ and $Ce(SO_4)_4^{4-}$ depending on the concentration of sulphate. From the study of the effect of $[H^+]$, $[HSO_4^-]$ or $[SO_4^{2-}]$ on rate, it was concluded that neutral $Ce(SO_4)_2$ is the reactive species on the present investigation. The inhibitory action² of HSO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} ions is explained as due to conversion of the reactive form of cerium(IV), $Ce(SO_4)_2$ to the unreactive species $Ce(SO_4)_4^{4-}$ and $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ according to the equilibria,

Effect of temperature : The reaction rate was markedly effected by the change in temperature from 35 to 50°. The value of activation energy (ΔE) in the bromide catalysed oxidation of dextrose was found to be $22.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

The kinetic results recorded in Tables 1-3 suggest that the oxidation proceeds through an intermediate complex of dextrose and cerium(IV).

The rate of reaction may be expressed in term of loss of concentration of Ce^{IV} . Hence rate is expressed as equation (1),

$$-\frac{d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = k_2 [X] \quad (1)$$

The mechanism leads to the rate law (2),

$$-\frac{d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1} + k_2} [Ce^{IV}] [M] \quad (2)$$

where M stands for dextrose.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ AND $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ ON REACTION VELOCITY CONSTANTTemp. = 40° , $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Dextrose}] = 12.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{KBr}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

$[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ $\times 10^2 \text{ M}$	k_1 $\times 10 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.00	0.00	4.00
0.50	0.00	2.50
1.00	0.00	2.40
1.50	0.00	2.25
2.00	0.00	2.00
0.00	5.00	2.96
0.00	10.00	2.67
0.00	12.50	2.56

Various experiments with different ratios of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ and $[\text{dextrose}]$ were performed. Estimation of excess of Ce^{IV} indicates that 24 moles of Ce^{IV} were required to oxidise one mole of dextrose in presence of bromide catalyst. The oxidation product in each case found to be CO_2 , was confirmed by lime-water test.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A standard stock solution of sodium thiosulphate

was prepared³. Ceric ammonim sulphate solution prepared in $2N \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was standardised iodometrically against standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The kinetics were followed by removing aliquot (5 ml) from the reaction mixture at different time intervals and the reaction was arrested by adding aqueous 5% KI (10 ml). The liberated iodine being equivalent to the concentration of the unreacted Ce^{IV} was titrated with standard solution of sodium thiosulphate.

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References

1. B. H. KISHAN, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, 1984; B. H. KISHAN and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1985, **62**, 654; G. HARGREAVES and L. H. SUTCLIFFE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 1105; T. J. HARDWICK and E. ROBERTSON, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 818, 828.
2. B. KISHNA and K. C. TIWARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 1178.
3. A. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', Longmans, London, 1961, p. 348.

